

GOLD

Growing energy crops on contaminated
land for biofuels and soil remediation

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D4.2

Communication and Dissemination Toolkit

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Project coordinator: CRES

This project has used a standard methodology already developed in NEGEM project (Grant Agreement number: 869192), following EU recommendations. Ad hoc modifications were added to comply with the Grant Agreement conditions for GOLD (Grant Agreement number: 101006873).

Partners

CRES - Centre for Renewable Energy Sources and Saving Foundation, Greece
AUA – Geoponiko Panepistimion Athinon, Greece
TUM - Technische Universität München, Germany
RE-CORD - Consorzio per la Ricerca e la Dimostrazione sulle Energie Rinnovabili, Italy
ETA - ETA Energia, Trasporti, Agricoltura, Italy
Uni-Lublin - Uniwersytet Marii Curie-Skłodowskiej, Poland
TNO - Nederlandse Organisatie Voor Toegepast Natuurwetenschappelijkonderzoek TNO, Netherlands
CERTH - ETHNIKO KENTRO EREVNAS KAI TECHNOLOGIKIS ANAPTYXIS, Greece
UNIBO - Alma Mater Studiorum - Università di Bologna, Italy
INRAE - Institut National de Recherche pour l'Agriculture, l'Alimentation et l'Environnement, France
YNCREA HDF – Junia, France
UNL - Universidade Nova de Lisboa, Portugal
ICL - Imperial College of Science Technology and Medicine, United Kingdom
WR - Stichting Wageningen Research, Netherlands
METE S.A. - METE AE METALLEFTIKI EMPORIKI TEHNIKI AE*MINING TRADING TECHNICAL SA, Greece
IITD - Indian Institute of Technology Delhi, India
HUNAN - Hunan Agricultural University, China
UDES - Université de Sherbrooke, Canada
IBFC - Institute of Bast Fiber Crops, Chinese Academy of Agricultural Sciences, China

Statement of Originality

This deliverable contains original unpublished work except where clearly indicated otherwise. Acknowledgement of previously published material and of the work of others has been made through appropriate citation, quotation or both.

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Executive Summary

This report describes the elements that constitute the visual identity of the GOLD project, including the project logo and the rules for its use, the colour palette and all the initial materials that were designed to ensure a coherent and homogeneous dissemination and communication of the project’s activities and results.

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Introduction

The GOLD Visual Identity and branding kit provides a tailored, recognizable way to present activities, events and results of the GOLD consortium towards all the project stakeholders and its target audience. The graphic elements were developed focusing on the project goals and the expected impacts.

The overarching aim of the GOLD project is to produce clean, low-ILUC biofuels by growing selected high-yielding crops on contaminated lands and, in the long term, return them to agricultural production. The visual identity of the project was elaborated in line with this goal. The present document describes the graphic elements that clearly identify the project, as well as a series of initial dissemination and communication tools that were designed in compliance with the visual identity. These include:

- Logo and graphic elements
- Template for slide presentations
- Template for poster presentation
- Project website
- Social media accounts

2. Project Logo and Graphic Elements

The logo designed for the GOLD project and approved by all the partners is based on the integration of three different elements: a geometrical shape halfway between a drop and a leaf (representing both the plants and biofuels produced in the scope of GOLD) which encompasses an upper-case G. The result is shown in figure 1.

Figure 1. Official GOLD logo.

An additional graphic element complements the logo to enrich the different communication and dissemination materials and is shown in figure 2:

Figure 2. Additional graphic element complementing the logo.

The logo set and accompanying guidelines for the use of its use will be available for all the partners in the member area of the website. The guidelines will contain all information needed concerning the graphic elements of the project, so that all the physical and digital materials are graphically consistent at consortium level. These also include colour specifications as shown in figure 3.

Green

HEX: 4E8F4A

R:78
G:143
B:74

C: 65
M: 0
Y: 65
K: 30

Yellow

HEX: FFDA45

R: 255
G: 218
B: 69

C: 0
M: 15
Y: 80
K: 0

Figure 3. Colour specifications of GOLD logo (Source: GOLD User Guideline for Visual Identity).

These colours have been chosen to recall the name of the project (Yellow) and to represent the plant species utilized in the scope of GOLD (Green).

The font used for GOLD's logo is Nasalization Heavy, while the font used for the text of content produced as an output of GOLD is Manrope. In documents that for design needs to be shared with the project team, it is recommended to use Calibri.

NASALIZATION HEAVY

AABBCCDDEEFFGGHHIIKKLLMMNNOOPPQQRRSSTTUUVVXXYYZZ
1234567890!"£\$%&'()*=?

Manrope Extralight

AaBbCcDdEeFfGgHhIiKkLlMmNnOoPpQqRrSsTtUuVvXxYyZz
1234567890!"£\$%&'()*=?

Manrope Light

AaBbCcDdEeFfGgHhIiKkLlMmNnOoPpQqRrSsTtUuVvXxYyZz
1234567890!"£\$%&'()*=?

Manrope Regular

AaBbCcDdEeFfGgHhIiKkLlMmNnOoPpQqRrSsTtUuVvXxYyZz
1234567890!"£\$%&'()*=?

Manrope Semibold

AaBbCcDdEeFfGgHhIiKkLlMmNnOoPpQqRrSsTtUuVvXxYyZz
1234567890!"£\$%&'()*=?

Manrope Extrabold

AaBbCcDdEeFfGgHhIiKkLlMmNnOoPpQqRrSsTtUuVvXxYyZz
1234567890!"£\$%&'()*=?

Figure 4. GOLD typeface details.

A full set of logo types has been created for use in different digital and print formats, as per fig. 5.

Full logo

Growing energy crops on contaminated
land for biofuels and soil remediation

Growing energy crops on contaminated
land for biofuels and soil remediation

Symbol only

Figure 5 Examples of GOLD logo's declinations

All communication materials will showcase:

- the GOLD logo facilitating the immediate and clear recognition of the project;
- the EU emblem¹: as foreseen by the EC, this is needed to acknowledge the origin of the funding;
- the official statement that the project has received funding from the Horizon 2020 Research and Innovation programme, through the following text:

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No. 101006873.

3. Website

An Initial landing page has already been published while the content for the complete website is under development. The full website will be available online no later than the end of August 2021 (M4) at the URL <https://www.gold-h2020.eu/>

The current structure of the website includes the following static pages:

- Home page
- About the project
- Activities
- Impacts
- Resources (for uploading of project deliverables, reports, articles etc.)
- Contacts

An Events page is also foreseen and will be shown as soon as the first public event will be announced.

The site has been created with Wordpress Content Management System and a News section is also available, where regular updates will be posted about the project activities, outputs, events and other relevant information.

¹ Source: https://ec.europa.eu/info/sites/info/files/use-emblem_en.pdf

The content for the website is being developed in line with the main indications received by the partners and that are explained more in details in the Plan for Exploitation, Dissemination and Communication (D9.5).

Figure 6. Screenshot of the landing page at gold-h2020.eu

4. Templates

After the elaboration of the logo, a series of templates were designed in compliance with the visual identity and are available for use by all the project partners. These include:

- a Word template for project deliverable/reports (which can be used as a basis for other documents e.g. project meetings agendas, etc.):

Deliverable Title

Partners

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YNCREA HDF – Junia, France
UNL - Universidade Nova de Lisboa, Portugal
ICL - Imperial College of Science Technology and Medicine, United Kingdom
WR - Stichting Wageningen Research, Netherlands
ΜΕΤΕ S.A. – ΜΕΤΕ ΑΕ ΜΕΤΑΛΛΕΥΤΙΚΗΣ ΕΜΠΟΡΙΚΗΣ ΤΕΧΝΙΚΗΣ ΑΕ*ΜΙΝΙΝΓ ΤΡΑΔΙΝΓ ΤΕΧΝΙΚΑΛ SΑ, Greece
IITD - Indian Institute of Technology Delhi, India
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Project Number: 101006873
Grant Agreement Number: 101006873
Programme: GOLD
Start date of Project: 15 April 2021
Duration: 48 months
Project coordinator: CRES

Executive Summary

Lorem ipsum dolor sit amet, consectetur adipiscing elit, sed do eiusmod tempor incididunt ut labore et dolore magna aliqua. Accumsan sit amet nulla facilis morbi tempus. Interdum consectetur libero id faucibus nisi tincidunt eget.

Please add **key policy relevant messages** here if relevant

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2. List of figures

Insert here if needed

- PowerPoint templates in 4:3 and 16:9 formats for slide presentations:

Fig. 10. Template (4:3) for slide presentations.

- A PowerPoint template in A0 format for poster presentations and a rollup banner for display at physical events (workshops, conferences, fairs):

Figure 11. Template for poster presentations.

5. Social media channels

Three dedicated social media accounts were created since Month 1 on Twitter (@gold_h2020), LinkedIn (<https://www.linkedin.com/company/gold-project-h2020/about/>) and Facebook (<https://www.facebook.com/GOLD-Project-H2020-110487614638871>). A YouTube Channel and a project profile on ResearchGate are foreseen later during the project.

Figure 12. – GOLD Twitter account.

Figure 13. GOLD LinkedIn page.

Figure 13. GOLD Facebook page.

6. Conclusion

By M3 the set of initial dissemination and communication materials and the digital tools are complete and operational. All these tools will be distributed to the Consortium partners and available in the member area of the project website. Any further updates and additions to these tools will be reported in future versions of this deliverable. These tools are instrumental for the implementation of the implementation of the Plan for Dissemination and Communication which is under preparation (D4.1 by M4), which identifies the key project messages defined by the Consortium, the target audience and the actions planned, to ensure the active promotion of the project and its activities, as well as the public disclosure of its project results.